

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17206961

Forensic Accounting And Pension Scheme Fraud Management In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined the effects of Forensic Accounting in managing the lingering problem of pension scheme frauds in Nigeria. As already captured in various literature, many pension reforms have been initiated in Nigeria, but none has been able to meet the expectations of the real beneficiaries, the average Nigerian pensioner. There is only one factor responsible for this, ‘‘Pension scheme frauds and corruption’’. The study adopted a survey research design to elicit responses from respondents. A 5-point Likert scale questionnaire was designed to get primary information about the level of pension scheme fraud and the ability of forensic accounting to solve the problem of prevalent fraud in the pension sector. The data collected were analyzed via the Pearson moment correlation coefficient (r). Findings reveal that pension fraud is on the increase in Nigeria and that there is a solution. The study recommended, among others, that forensic accountants be engaged to help strengthen the internal control and payment systems of the various pension fund Administrators (PFA).

Keywords: Forensic Accounting, Pension Scheme, Frauds, Corruption.

1.0. INTRODUCTION

The pension scheme in Nigeria has been unable to deliver on its mandate of ensuring a better life after retirement for retirees. Even with proper planning by way of monthly contributions by employees during their active years in service, pension fraud makes the future of pensioners and old people very uncertain and unpredictable. According to Nwanna and Ogbonna (2019), despite the challenges of low income and savings as well as social responsibilities faced by Nigerian workers, they still ensure that their pension contribution is remitted. However, they tend not to fully reap their pension investment as expected due to incessant fraudulent activities in the pension schemes (Ogbonna & Nwanna 2019).

The noticeable incidences of pension fraud in Nigeria necessitated the introduction of the present contribution pension scheme, which is a child born out of the 2004 Pension Reform Act in Nigeria. Experts are of the view that the contributory pension system is better than the old pension scheme, except for the high incidences of mismanagement and fraud. Amaka, Chizoba, and Edirin (2017), explain that a critical look into the pension affairs of most Ministries, Departments, and Agencies (MDAs) of Government showcases the extent to which pension fraud negatively affects the success of the contributory pension scheme in Nigeria. Furthermore, they observed that the main perpetrators of pension frauds are the top management and the motivating factors for such frauds are not different from factors that cause other types of fraud (Amaka, Chizoba & Edirin 2017);

Tasker (2012) opined that pension thieves often feel that they have a need, such as the desire to acquire material goods. While this dangerous fraud continues in a great manner, it is believed that, if not checked or managed, it could lead to a wide range of problems, including the government’s inability to achieve

success in the new contributory pension scheme. It is on this basis that this paper intends to examine the effects of forensic accounting in managing the vexed issue of pension fraud and corruption in Nigeria.

1.1. Objectives of the study

The objectives of this study are:

- To determine the degree of pension fraud in Nigeria
- Ascertain the effects of forensic Accounting as an anti-fraud measure in managing pension frauds in Nigeria.

Hypothesis one:

Ho1: There is evidence of a high degree of pension fraud in Nigeria

Ha1: There is no evidence of a high degree of pension fraud in Nigeria

Hypothesis Two

Ho1: The introduction of Forensic Accounting as an anti-fraud measure can enhance the management of pension fraud in Nigeria

Ha, The introduction of Forensic Accounting as an anti-fraud measure cannot enhance the management of pension fraud in Nigeria.

2.0. Review of Related Literature

2.1. Conception Framework

2.1.1 Concept and Meaning of Pension

The term pension has been explained by different policymakers and researchers at different times to mean the agreement between employers and retirees at retirement (Nwanna & Ogbonna 2019)

According to Odia and Okoye (2012), a pension happens in a system where individuals contribute to an identified scheme, a certain proportion of their earnings/entitlements during their years of active service. Such contributions provide a stream of income for the contributor at retirement (Odia & Okoye 2012). In his view, Fapohunda (2013) opined that pension is the amount agreed upon by both the employers and the employees to be jointly set aside to ensure that workers are not financially bankrupt in their old age (i.e. post-retirement) (Fapohunda, 2013). In the same vein, Eme, Uche, and Uche (2014) in Amaka, Chizoba, and Ediwin (2017) describe pension as a periodic income in annuity payment made at or after the retirement of the employees who may have to be due or eligible for the said benefits as a result of either age or completed service years (i.e. 60 years of age or 35 years of active service)

2.1.2 The Nigerian Pension Industry: Historical Perspective

The history of the Nigerian Pension Industry can be traced back to the pension ordinance of 1951 which took effect retrospectively from January 1946. According to Uzoma (1989), the vital information contained in the 1946 pension ordinance ranges from the identification of who a Native Administration Servant is to the nature of benefits (gratuity and pension) and eligibility conditions (Uzoma 1989). Historically, the pioneer private sector pension scheme was set up by Nigerian Breweries in 1954 which was followed in 1961 with the setting up of the National Provident Fund (NPF), a fund that was specifically meant for pensionable private sector employees (Nwanna & Ogbonna 2019)

In 1979, the Basic Pension Decree 102 which established a civil service pension scheme for the public sector was promulgated. In 1993, the military government of General Babangida established the Nigerian Social Insurance Trust Fund (NSITF). This fund came to replace the National Provident Fund (NPF) of 1961. The NSITF mandated employees and employers to contribute 6% of their basic income. At the return of democratic governance, President Obasanjo's government came up with the Pension Reform Act of 2004. The reform followed the Chile pension Reforms of 1981. Within a short time of its enactment, the 2004 Contributory Pension Reform Act became very popular. This act gave birth to the establishment of the National Pension Commission. A Commission saddled with the responsibility of gathering and

managing the national pension funds. However, of great relevance is the fact that, before the enactment of this Act, the national pension Liability deficit was over ₦2 Trillion which was unable to sustain the “Pay as you go system.

According to Nwanna and Ogbonna (2019), five years after the enactment of the 2004 Pension Act (i.e 2009), the registered retirement saving account (RSA) holders had grown up to 4.01 million pensions and pension fund Assets of ₦1.5 trillion. In 2012, pension Fund Assets was ₦2.9 trillion. By 2013 Pencom had registered 5.92 million contributors and generated ₦3.82 trillion investible funds (Pencom, 2013). As of 2019, the pension fund Assets have grown far beyond ₦7.6 trillion, and as of 2023, the asset base had risen to over N23 trillion. (Pencom, 2023)

2.1.3 Concept of Fraud

Financial Fraud has been defined by different authors in different literature. According to the Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary, Fraud can be defined as the crime of deceiving somebody to get money or goods illegally. Williams (2005) describes fraud to include bribery, nepotism, cronyism, political donation, kickbacks, artificial pricing, and frauds of all kinds. The characteristics of financial crime are in exhaustive. The foremost anti-graft agency in Nigeria, the Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC) Act (2004), defined fraud as an illegal act that violates existing legislation and these include any form of fraud, narcotic drug, trafficking, money laundering, embezzlement, bribery looting, child labor, illegal oil bunkering, and illegal mining tax evasion, foreign exchange malpractices including counterfeiting currency, theft of intellectual property and piracy, open market abuse, dumping of toxic waste and prohibited goods, etc. this definition is all-embracing and it includes crimes in corporate entities and all others enumerated by various authors and researchers (EFCC 2004).

According to Karimi (2002) and Ajie and Ezi (2000) in Raymond. Nkiru and Jane (2016) Fraud is classified into two different mediums. These are the nature of fraudsters and the medium employed in carrying out the fraud. On the nature of fraudsters, frauds may come in three forms, namely, internal, external, and mixed frauds. Internal frauds comprise frauds carried out by members of staff including directors of the organization, External frauds are frauds committed by fraudsters who have no relationship with the organization and mixed frauds are frauds that occur with the collaboration of both the internal staff of the organization and outsiders. Furthermore, Karwai (2002) opined that it is difficult to identify the actual causes of fraud; because present-day fraud is committed by a complex web of conspiracy that often makes it strenuous to identify the actual cause (Kawai 2002).

2.1.4 Overview of Pension Fraud in Nigeria

Nigeria has witnessed notable cases of pension fraud in the last decade. These cases have cost the nation large sums of money meant for the upkeep of the aged and pensioners in the country. Notable among these cases is the MAINA GATE. However, before the emergence of the alleged pension frauds of Abdulrasheed Maina, several other fraud cases had already appeared on the front pages of Nigeria Newspapers. It is believed that over 273 Billion have been stolen through pension frauds in Nigeria between 2005 and 2011 (Amaka, Chizoba & Edirin (2017).

Additionally, Akinkuotu and Onuba (2016) in Amaka, Chizoba and Edirin (2017) reported that the Nigerian foremost anti-graft agency, the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) arrested one Mrs. N. Mayshak alongside her 3 accomplices (namely: P. Iyogun, Y. Yousonfu, and R. Imunkhe) for stealing over N2.5 Billion from the pension fund. They further reported that the take-off grant for the newly established PTAD of about N500 million was embezzled by the then D.G. of PTAD through a fictitious procurement fraud. Furthermore, Amaka, Chizoba, and Edirin (2017), reported that through a complex web, Abdulrasheed Maina was accused of laundering Billions of Naira along with his family members, account officers, associates, and corporate entities and contractors. Accordingly, it was further reported by the researchers that with a letter addressed to the Attorney General of the Federation by the EFCC, the PRTT under the care of Abdulrasheed Maina spent a humongous sum of N5, 761,150,608.44 on fictitious contracts.

Furthermore, he paid about N829, 902,260.40 to ghost workers, and 192,825,310.99 were siphoned under the guise of payment made to pension boards of various states. Maina A. A was removed from office and is still being prosecuted up to date.

2.1.5 Motivation for Pension Frauds

In the view of KPMG (2005), the causes of pension fraud are not likely to be driven by the desire to reach a certain financial height in life, but rather to achieve personal financial gain (KPMG 2005). According to CIMA (2009), such personal motivations are driven by greed, personality, and temperament. CIMA (2009) further observed that individual may be pushed to commit pension fraud when they are confronted with personal financial problems that are beyond their control. Moreover, Osisioma (2009) and Okoye (2016) enumerated several motivational factors for occupational fraud which includes

- Desire to live above one's means of livelihood
 - Extreme cravings for personal gains
 - Increase personal debts
 - Poor pay compared to job schedule
 - Undue pressure from family members and friends and
 - Uncontrollable desire for gambling
- (Osisioma, 2009), (Okoye 2016)

2.1.6 Types of Pension Fraud Scheme in Nigeria

According to KPMG (2005) cited in Amaka, Chizoba, and Edirin (2017), the major examples of frauds perpetuated against pension schemes in Nigeria include:

1. **Beneficial Fraud:** This kind of fraud occurs to the benefit of the family members or the relatives of the fraudster. It is a situation where the family members continue to benefit beyond their entitlement.
2. **Third-party Fraud:** This kind of pension fraud occurs when the theft from the pension scheme funds happens via the presentation of fake or altered bank cheques.
3. **Trustees Fraud:** This is when the trustees the custodian of the pension fraud themselves steal from the scheme through the misuse of its assets.
4. **Staff Fraud:** This type of fraud takes place when the staff or officials who are saddled with the responsibilities of managing the funds and assets of the scheme engage in fraudulent acts, such as creating fictitious pensioners/beneficial accounts and transferring money to themselves through such fictitious accounts.

In addition to the above, ACCA (2003) outlined other examples of fraud schemes in Pension organizations including (a) Misappropriation of pension funds on Assets; (b) Nonpayment of contributions by the employers (c) Bouncing of the pension fund by the employer, etc. (ACCA 2003)

2.2. Concept of Forensic Accounting

Forensic or investigative accounting is the application of financial skill and investigative mentality to unresolved issues, conducted within the context of the rules of evidence. As a special discipline, it encompasses fraud knowledge, financial expertise, and sound knowledge of the legal system (Bologna and Lindquist 1987). According to Olola (2016), forensic accounting is a tripartite practice of utilizing accounting auditing and investigative skills to assist in legal matters. However, Apostolou, Hassell, and Webber (2000) defined forensic accounting as a specialized field of accounting that describes engagements that result from litigation. Forensic accounting can therefore be viewed as an aspect of accounting that is suitable for legal review and offers the highest level of assurance (Apostolou, Hassell & Webber 2000).

One of the most striking definitions of forensic accounting is the one done by Dhar and Sakar (2010) where they defined forensic accounting as the application of accounting concepts and techniques, to legal problems. It demands reporting, where fraud is established and the report is considered as evidence in the court of law in administrative and legal proceedings (Dhar & Sakar 2010). According to Bhasin (2007),

forensic accountants are trained to look beyond the numbers and deal with business realities of situations. He further asserted that the activities of forensic accountants involve: investigating and analyzing financial evidence, developing computerized applications to assist in the analysis and presentation of financial evidence; exhibits, and collections of documents, and assisting in legal proceedings; including testifying in court as an expert witness (Bhasin 2007)

2.2.1. Pension Fraud: Forensic Accounting as Antidote

Forensic accounting is a globally accepted profession, which deals with the application of accounting principles and concepts to solving financial fraud issues including legal disputes. The Nigerian pension sector is and has been infested with monumental financial fraud in the past. Forensic accountants are useful for investigating the theft of pension funds resulting from yearly incidents as a result of poor or inadequate financial and internal control. Hence forensic accountants are professional in curbing thefts, and suspicious pension payment reporting. The rise in the demand for improved pension funds management accountability has created a special and timely opportunity for accountants and their professional bodies to join forces to eradicate pension fraud in Nigeria.

Through his training and expertise, the forensic accountant is best qualified to save the Nigerian pension sector in areas such as pension fraud/money laundering, Audit for compliance with anti-fraud measures, protection of the pension fund Budgeting processes, planning for pension fund sustainability, reforming procurement procedures in the pension, watching pension spending, and taking practical steps for improving investment of pension assets. As an advocate of truth and transparency, the forensic accountant can assist in ensuring spending priorities, and revenue transparency; thereby reducing the opportunities for corruption in the Nigerian pension sector.

2.3. Theoretical Framework

There are several fraud theories, which explain why people commit fraud. However, for this paper, we shall be combing the fraud Triangle, Diamond, and fraud management theories to explain the psychological and indeed other key reasons why individuals engage in fraudulent activities. According to Peterson and Zikmuud (2004); and Wells (2007), the fraud triangle theory is the most celebrated theory that examines why financial and economic crimes are perpetrated by individuals. In addition, Albredit, Turnbull, Zhang, and Skousen (2010) described this theory by explaining that fraud is usually committed by an individual when there is pressure from many situations (e.g. financial, material, and even family and peer pressure), a high opportunity presents itself, coupled with low integrity. Thus, these key three conditions are widely regarded as the core motivating factors for the perpetuation of Financial and Economic Crimes.

However, in addition to the above, Wolfe and Hermansom (2004) developed the theory of fraud Diamond. This theory enunciates that the fraud factors enumerated in the fraud triangle theory (Pressure, Opportunity & Rationalization) are not enough to carry out a fraud act. They indicated that one may have all the attributes inherent in the fraud triangle but without the ability or capability, they may not be able to carry out the fraud. Therefore, they expanded the fraud triangle by adding the capability to make it a fraud Diamond. In other words, the fraud Diamond theory posits that capability and or personality traits are necessary for engagement or not engaging in fraud.

The fraud Management Lifecycle was developed by Wilhelm (2004). The theory has eight interrelated stages aimed at managing fraud. These eight stages are prevention deterrence, detection, mitigation, analysis, policy-making, investigation, and prosecution. These stages are all independent actions that can be performed simultaneously to manage fraud. It is connected to this study in so much that it can aid the forensic accountant in outlining his steps when engaged in managing fraud acts (E.g. Pension frauds)

2.4. Empirical Studies

Amaka, Chizoba, and Ediwin (2017) researched the anatomy of pension fraud in Nigeria: Its motives, management, and future of the Nigerian Pension scheme. The study determined how the administration of

the pension scheme could be effectively managed in Nigeria to reduce the apparent fraudulent practices in the scheme. The study adopted a survey research design and data were analyzed via multiple Regression Analysis models. The findings reveal that despite the provisions of the Pension Reform Act, the intent to commit pension fraud has not been reduced. The study recommended among others that the Pension Reform Act should be amended to further discourage acts of pension fraud by putting severe punitive measures on culprits. Eme, Uche, and Uche (2014), investigated the police pension scam that was investigated by the Senate of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. The main aim of the study was to unearth the details and background information about the scam. The investigation and findings of the study revealed that public servants in the Nigerian Police Pension Board, massively looted funds meant for the payment of retirees of the Nigerian Police.

Nwagwo (2014) examined the new contributory pension scheme and how it could be managed through transparency and accountability. The study employed the survey design method. The main objective of the study was to ascertain whether transparency and accountability were maintained in the management of the consolidated pension funds. Data was obtained through a questionnaire and analyzed via T-Test statistics. Findings from the study revealed that, until then, in managing pension funds, transparency and Accountability have been maintained. It therefore recommended that all pension funds should be insured to safeguard them. Nwana and Ogbonna (2019) examined the evolution of pension management in Nigeria and its importance to the economy. The study used secondary data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria's Annual statistical bulletin between 2004 and 2018. It employed multiple regression analysis in analyzing the data. Findings from the analysis reveal that pension management affects Economic growth in Nigeria within the period under review. The study recommended amongst others that pension management should be efficiently improved upon to address the relatively few number of retirement savings accounts in Nigeria.

Omah, Anifowose, and Ogundina (2013), researched Pension Fraud: A concomitant debacle in public sector economy – Nigeria's Perspective. The study used a survey method to obtain public opinion on the impact of pension fraud on the public sector economy. The analysis of the findings revealed that there are many fraud managers in public sector pension management. The study therefore recommended that there should be a restructuring of pension administration in Nigeria. Iyortsuun and Akpusugh (2013) examined how the lifestyle of employees could be properly managed after disengagement from service. The study used primary and secondary sources to gather its data. Furthermore, the paper employed the stratified method of sampling to select the required sample of the study, and the descriptive and inferential statistics were centered on the results computed through simple percentages. The study through its findings concluded that the core challenges of pension administration in Nigeria which are fraud, corruption, inefficiency, poor governance, and regulatory challenges had impeded the success of the Nigerian pension reform.

3.0. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the survey method. The study's population consists of 457 auditors, pensioners, Pencom Officials, Accountants, Custodians of Pension funds, and public servants of the selected Ministries, Departments, and Agencies across the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja-Nigeria. The research data was obtained using structured questionnaires that were administered randomly to the sample population. However, only 245 questionnaires were retrieved from the respondents for analysis. The options for answering the questions are "strongly Agree, Agree, Uncertain, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree". They were weighted 5,4,3,2, & 1 respectively. The responses to the data obtained were analyzed using Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient (r).

3.1. Model Specification

As stated above, the model for this study Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient was employed to analyze the data of the study. This model measures the strength of the linear relationship between the

two variables X and y estimated by a simple correlation coefficient denoted by r. It is given by the following formula:

$$r = \frac{\sum xy}{\sqrt{\sum x^2 \sum y^2}} \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 1}$$

Where

r = person moment coefficient correlation

x = weight attached to response

y = Frequency of response

$\sqrt{\quad}$ = square roots

Decision Rule:

- The person’s correlation coefficient r may assume any value from -1 to 1 (i.e., $-1 \leq r \leq 1$) depending on the direction and strength of the relationship.
- If $r = 0$, then there is no linear relationship (zero correlation)
- The closer r is to 1, the stronger the positive correlation while the closer r is to 0, the weaker the correlation.

4.0. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1. Data Presentation

Table 1: Response to Question 1: Pensions Related Frauds and corruption are on the rise in Nigeria

Response	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Strongly Agree	106	43
Agree	99	40
Uncertain	10	04
Disagree	26	11
Strongly Disagree	4	02
Total	245	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2: Response to Question 1: Application of Forensic Accounting Techniques can serve as an anti-pension Fraud Management measure

Response	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Strongly Agree	115	47
Agree	86	35
Uncertain	15	6
Disagree	19	8
Strongly Disagree	10	4
Total	245	100%

Source: Field survey, 2024

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis 1

The data in Table 1 and Equation 1 specified the model that was used to correlate r and test hypothesis 1 which is

H01: There is Evidence of a High Degree of Pension Fraud and Corruption in Nigeria.

Table 3: Computation of Pearson Product-moment Correlation Coefficient (r)

	X	Y	X=x-x	Y=y-y	Xy	X ²	Y ²
Strongly Agree	5	106	2	57	114	4	3249
Agree	4	99	1	50	50	1	2500
Uncertain	3	10	0	-39	0	0	152
Disagree	2	26	-1	-23	23	1	529
Strongly Disagree	1	4	-2	45	90	4	2025
Total	15	245			277	10	9,824

Source: Research computation, 2024

$$\text{Since } x = \frac{\sum x}{n} = \frac{55}{5} = 11$$

$$\text{And } y = \frac{\sum y}{n} = \frac{245}{5} = 49$$

$$\text{From Equation 1: } r = \frac{\sum xy}{\sqrt{\sum x^2 \sum y^2}} = \frac{277}{313.43} = r = 0.883$$

Hypothesis 2:

The introduction of Forensic Accounting as an anti-fraud measure can enhance the management of pension fraud in Nigeria

Table 4: Computation of pension product-moment correlation coefficient (r)

	X	Y	X=x-x	Y=y-y	Xy	X ²	Y ²
Strongly Agree	5	115	2	66	132	4	4356
Agree	4	86	1	37	37	1	1369
Uncertain	3	15	0	-34	0	0	1156
Disagree	2	19	-1	-30	30	1	900
Strongly Disagree	1	10	-2	-39	78	4	1521
Total	15	245			277	10	9,302

Source: Researchers computation, 2024

$$\text{Since } x = \frac{\sum x}{n} = \frac{15}{5} = 3$$

$$\text{And } y = \frac{\sum y}{n} = \frac{245}{5} = 49$$

$$\text{From Equation 1, } r = \frac{\sum xy}{\sqrt{\sum x^2 \sum y^2}} = \frac{277}{\sqrt{10 \times 9302}} = \frac{277}{304.99} = r = 0.908$$

4.2 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Examine the data in Table 1 and employing the equation of the model, it was observed that the Pearson product-moment correlation (r) read 0.883. From the set decision rule, the closer r is to 1 the stronger the positive correlation. This indicates that most respondents are of the view that there exists a great measure of pension fraud and corruption in Nigeria. Applying the same model and decision rule in data in Table 2. The Pearson product movement correlation coefficient (r) read 0.908. R, here is closer to 1 implying the strength of the relationship. This implies that the majority of the respondents do agree that the

introduction of Forensic accounting as an anti-fraud measure could help in managing pension frauds in Nigeria.

5.0. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The discussion on the impact of Forensic accounting as the panacea to pension fraud management in Nigeria x-rays the concept of pension and pension frauds, and forensic accounting, and analyzes the various pension fraud types perpetrated against the Nigerian pension scheme. Efforts were made to find the level of fraud in the pension system and ascertain whether the introduction of forensic experts to man the payment and accounting systems of pension organizations in Nigeria could aid in managing the pension fraud saga. By using the survey design, the data gathered were subjected to analysis and the results show overwhelmingly that there exists financial fraud in a monumental proportion of the pension industry. It was also observed that forensic experts' knowledge could be brought to bear to manage the lingering financial fraud problems in the Nigerian pension scheme.

Recommendations

Arising from the above conclusions, the following recommendation is thus made;

1. The Nigerian government should ensure strong promotion and engagement of forensic accountants to assist in exterminating the rot and challenges associated with the management of the Nigerian Pension Scheme which continuously breeds fraud and corruption.
2. The government should be truly committed to the fight against pension fraud. This can be achieved through strict oversight of the activities of the various pension fund administrators.
3. The government should encourage a stress-less process of application for the collection of retirees' entitlements. This will eliminate unnecessary bureaucracy which often breeds corruption and fraud.
4. Finally, forensic accountants, because they can make noticeable contributions as part of governance structures concerning reforms in the pension sector, should be engaged to help chart the way forward in areas such as the establishment of a comprehensive corporate governance policy that will ensure efficient management of pensions funds; creating through relevant policies, a positive work arrangement to prevent frauds and corruption in the operations of the various pension fund administrators (PFA's).

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